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Supervisory Practices and Teachers' Efficacy in the Division of Cabuyao

Alyssa Joone B. Capulong*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study explores the evolution of supervision in educational settings, focusing on the transition from traditional inspection methods to more developmental and clinical supervisory practices. Using a descriptive correlational research design, the study systematically examines the relationship between supervisory practices and teachers' efficacy in the Division of Cabuyao City. A self-constructed questionnaire, validated by experts and utilizing a Likert scale, was administered to public school teachers in Cabuyao to assess their perceptions of supervisory practices and their own efficacy. The findings indicate that supervisors, school heads, and master teachers in Cabuyao City public schools actively engage in pre-observation, classroom observation, and post-conference analysis, which are crucial for fostering a supportive learning environment. These practices include detailed pre-observation preparations, the use of COT-RPMS rating sheets, and constructive feedback during post-observation conferences. Additionally, the study reveals that elementary teachers in Cabuyao City demonstrate high levels of student engagement, effective instructional strategies, and strong classroom management skills. The research identifies a significant correlation between supervisory practices and teachers' efficacy, particularly in areas such as pre-observation conferences and classroom management. This suggests that enhanced supervisory practices lead to improved teacher performance, highlighting the need for a compilation of best supervisory practices to guide effective teacher supervision. The study contributes to the understanding of how supervisory practices impact teachers' professional growth and offers insights for improving educational supervision in public schools.

Keywords: *supervisory, practices, efficacy, education, traditional*

Introduction

Historically, supervision was initially connoted as inspection of what teachers are teaching and what students were learning inside the classroom. In the second half of the century, the activity evolved into practices that involved different forms of clinical supervision (Education Encyclopedia, 2019). This eventually became a program for improving the educational environment and the teaching profession as a result of different studies and researches initiated by both educators and psychologists.

As Kaminado (2010) defined, supervision is leadership for the improvement instruction and ultimately student learning. These definitions suggest that the role of supervision is to improve teaching and learning through a deliberate emphasis on ways and means of instilling excellence in the quality instruction.

In the course of its development, supervision has become a program for studying and improving the atmosphere that surrounds the teaching and learning process. It exists as a formal activity initiated by groups of individuals that provide assistance to teachers to continuously flourish in the classroom. Its goal is to facilitate coordination, motivation, and direction of the teachers' professional growth and development. As Sharma (2014) puts it, supervision touches the teacher, the learning condition, the learning material, and the learner directly, thus in totality, it aims for the improvement of the teaching-learning process. Through the course of time, it developed and evolved into a systematized activity initiated by individuals who serve as leaders that provide assistance to teachers to continuously improve their competencies in the classroom.

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilized the descriptive correlational method of research. According to Adanza et al. (2014), the descriptive method of research is designed to gather information about present conditions, status or trend, and dealing with what are prevailing. This systematically describes a situation and condition or area of interest factually and accurately. This is the most appropriate design for the study since this assesses the status of the independent and dependent variables. This is appropriate to the study since this identifies the independent and dependent variables which may be significantly related to each other.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the teachers of the Division of Cabuyao. The table that follows provides the number of respondents who were the participants from public schools in the City of Cabuyao.

Instrument

The researcher formulated a questionnaire as its main instrument which was patterned after Instructional Supervision: Standards, Procedures and Tools – DepEd Programs. The first part included the respondents' information. The second part dealt with the level of

manifestation of developmental supervisory practices. The third part assessed teachers' efficacy. For easy administration, scoring and assessment of the survey questionnaire, the Likert scale was utilized to easily obtain the responses. Four (4) point scale ranging from four (4) being the highest and one (1) as the lowest were the choices of the respondents.

To validate the questionnaire, the researcher sought the assistance of the experts in research who were the school research adviser, statistician, and language editor to establish content and construct validity. The researcher consulted some teachers to check the clarity and validity of the questions. The questionnaire went through several editing during its validation period. When the consequent corrections and suggestions had been incorporated, the final draft of the questionnaire was readied, and consequently, administered to the respondents of the study.

Procedure

A letter of request was sent to the City Schools Division of Cabuyao asking permission for the researcher to be allowed to conduct the study to the selected public schools in DepEd Cabuyao.

Moreover, individual letters of request were given to the selected school heads of the public school. This letter sought approval regarding the collection of assessment of teachers.

Afterwards, the researcher provided three sets of questionnaires to the teachers who assessed the supervisory practices of supervisors, school heads and master teachers. The questionnaires were retrieved immediately and tabulated for analysis and interpretation of data.

Data Analysis

The following were the statistical treatment applied to the study by the statistician using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS): Frequency and percentage were used to determine the level of manifestation of developmental supervisory practices and teachers' efficacy. Bon-Ferroni for independent samples was used to determine the difference between the assessments of the supervisors, school heads, and master teachers. The mean and four-point Likert Scale were used to describe the level of manifestation of developmental supervisory practices of and teachers' efficacy of the public schools in City Schools Division of Cabuyao. To establish relationship between the level of manifestation of developmental supervisory practices and teachers' efficacy, Pearson Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was used.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical concerns followed by the researcher as those were taken into account throughout this paper. Consent was asked so that confidentiality was assured. All the necessary details were explained by the researcher for them to understand their role upon the completion of the study. Information personal to the co-researchers had been assured to have its confidentiality.

Results and Discussion

Based on the data gathered and after careful and thorough analysis of the investigation, the following are the findings of the study in summarized form.

Level of Manifestation of Supervisory Practices among Public Elementary Schools Supervisors, School Heads, and Master Teachers of Cabuyao City as assessed by the Teachers

In terms of level of manifestation of supervisory practices in pre-observation conference, the general composite assessment was 3.43 interpreted as Manifested.

In terms of level of manifestation of supervisory practices in classroom observation, it has gotten the general composite mean of 3.48 verbally interpreted as Manifested.

In terms of level of manifestation of supervisory practices in analysis and strategy session, it reveals a composite mean of 3.35 verbally interpreted as Manifested.

In terms of level of manifestation of supervisory practices in conference session, it reveals a composite mean of 3.46 interpreted as Manifested.

In terms of level of manifestation of supervisory practices in post-conference analysis, the overall composite is 3.48 interpreted as Manifested.

Teachers' Efficacy in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as assessed by the teachers.

In terms of teachers' efficacy in the Division of Cabuyao City as to student management, the general assessment is 3.69 and verbally interpreted as Highly Manifested.

In terms of teachers' efficacy in the Division of Cabuyao City as to instructional strategies, general assessment is 3.74 and verbally interpreted as Highly Manifested.

In terms of teachers' efficacy in the Division of Cabuyao City as to instructional strategies, this reveals a composite mean of 3.74 and verbally interpreted as Highly Manifested.

Significant Relationship between Level of Manifestation of Supervisory Practices among Public Elementary Supervisors, School heads and Master Teachers and Level of Teachers' Efficacy

There is significant relationship between pre-observation conference and teachers' efficacy as to students' engagement, instructional strategies and classroom management. There is also significant relationship between analysis and strategy session and teachers' efficacy in terms of classroom management. Their probability values of .002, .000, .002, and .004 respectively are all less than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

On the other hand, there is no significant relationship between the level of manifestation of supervisory practices as to classroom observation, analysis and strategy session, conference and post conference analysis, and teachers' efficacy as to students' engagements, instructional strategies, and classroom management. The probability values are all greater than the level of significance at .05.

The Proposed Compilation of Best Supervisory Practices

As an output, a compilation of best supervisory practices is proposed to easily assess the teachers in supervising teachers' performance as a result of their supervisors' good supervisory skills.

Conclusions

Based on the aforementioned findings of the study, the following conclusions have been derived:

That the supervisors, school heads, and master teachers of public schools in Cabuyao City have manifested supervisory practices when it comes to pre-observation practices based on the opinion and observation of public-school teachers. Teachers also observe that the school supervisors, school heads, and master teachers are very particular in submission of Teachers Pre-Observation forms and preparation for the formal school visitation and observation. That the supervisory practices of public elementary schools of Cabuyao City as assessed by the teachers in terms of classroom observation have been very evident based on its interpretation of manifested. Public school administrators of Cabuyao evidently use COT-RPMS rating sheet to evaluate the performance of teachers but not that particular with checking teacher's daily lesson log.

That supervisory practices of supervisors, school heads, and master teachers in the public elementary schools of Cabuyao City when it comes to analysis and strategy session have been manifested. They have been particular with the recognizing teacher's strengths and needs and provide opportunities growth in a supportive learning environment as well as encouraging teachers to inquire on good practices and to pursue better alternatives for improvement teaching and learning.

That supervisors, school heads, and master teachers have manifested developmental supervisory practices as to conference session. They propose innovations to improve instruction of teachers in delivering their subjects. That supervisory practices of supervisors, school heads, and master teachers in the public elementary schools of Cabuyao City when it comes to post-conference analysis have been manifested. They have been particular with the commending teacher for the strengths in the actual teaching and other observed indicators as well as giving oral and written feedback to student teachers after each formal observation.

That the elementary teachers in the Division of Cabuyao City have manifested high engagement with their students for them to feel motivated, confidence, creativity, understanding, and value for learning. That the elementary teachers in the Division of Cabuyao City highly manifest instructional strategies. Teachers highly implement alternative teaching strategies, provide an alternative explanation or example when students are confused, measure pupil comprehension, and use a variety of assessment strategies. That when it comes to classroom management, elementary teachers of the Division of Cabuyao are able to highly control disruptive behavior in the classroom, make their expectations clear about student behavior, highly establish routines to keep activities running smoothly, and calm a student who is disruptive or noisy.

That pre-observation conference and teachers' efficacy as to students' engagement, instructional strategies and classroom management are associated. Analysis and strategy session and teachers' efficacy in terms of classroom management are also connected or associated with each other. Supervisory practices and teachers' efficacy when it come to pre-observation conference are greatly associated to each other. Analysis and strategy session and teachers' efficacy in terms of classroom management are also associated to one another. The higher the observance of supervisory practices among heads, the higher teachers' efficacy and vice versa. That the proposed compilation of best supervisory practices is necessary to objectively assess in supervising the teachers' performance.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Alyssa Joone B. Capulong
Niugan Elementary School
Department of Education – Philippines